

Online Education Pedagogy beyond Face-To-Face Modes: Challenges and Academic Achievements

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Received : 03/01/2023

1st BPR : 16/01/2023

2nd BPR : 31/01/2023

Accepted : 16/02/2023

Abstract

All educational institutions worldwide have been closed since the COVID-19 pandemic started. The outbreak has interfered with people's and students' traditional way of life. People are beginning to enter the virtual world everywhere. To provide classes to students during this pandemic, many schools have gone online. Online learning was initially developed to enhance distance education by improving student-teacher contact, but it is now frequently used as an adjunct to conventional in-person instruction. In this article, I describe perceptions of online and face-to-face learning settings and contrast their differences, similarities, and relationships, particularly in light of academic accomplishment.

Key words : Face-to-face mode, academic achievement, Online Education.

Abstract:

Introduction:

All colleges and institutions are offering online courses during the Covid-19 epidemic. But a year later, students still long for traditional classroom settings and want to return to high school and college to engage in face-to-face instruction. Due to their ease, students are more inclined to pick online courses than traditional classes. In addition, learners are now more responsible for acquiring their information thanks to advancements in e-learning. Compared to face-to-face settings, better e-learning can be enhanced through educational technology, such as videos, cell phones, learning management systems, and social networking sites.

ICT (information and communication technologies) have changed educational pedagogy and presented the field of education with new difficulties. Yet, it goes beyond simply educating or conventionally disseminating information at a minimal cost for lecturers and teachers. Hence, staff training swiftly reacted to online learning programs. As a result, teachers are utilizing brand-new, cutting-edge technologies to conduct lessons and communicate with pupils throughout the pandemic. Numerous institutions and universities provide teacher development programs and training to encourage teachers to select an appropriate learning platform that they are accustomed to. In addition, universities and schools are starting to adopt various specialized software for teaching and learning processes to support teachers. The current study compares students' experiences and results between traditional in-person and online learning.

First response for Digitalization

The schools and universities halted regular classes as soon as India was severely affected by COVID-19. Several people began providing online seminars to find a remedy as they were concerned about what would occur next. In addition, independent, private groups have offered online lectures and classes. As a result, there is minimal effect on academic achievement. Nonetheless, the switch from in-

person instruction to online instruction has impacted both students and teachers. The change to online learning had to be acknowledged by higher education instructors. On the other hand, if the lockdown lasts for a long time, there will be a need for more substantial Computer infrastructure for teaching and learning. In addition, teachers and students must both receive further training.

Digital Evolution

When it comes to online classrooms, educational institutions must first decide what policies and procedures to implement. You have two options due to this—either a live session or a recorded session, but not both. In the first type, recorded lessons are made available to the public, enabling students to look them up and access them whenever and wherever they like. A MOOC is a term used to describe this instruction (MOOC). The second form consists of live online classes where instructors employ a variety of software programs, including Zoom Meet, Google Class Room, Cisco Webex, etc. However, education organizations and students require a high-speed internet connection to hold online classes. Students will also require a smartphone, PC, or laptop for regular attendance and online courses. Teachers experienced with online learning procedures and a dependable and appropriate IT infrastructure are needed in schools and colleges.

National Programs for online education

In India, the Ministry of Human Resources Development (MHRD) has undertaken numerous projects to offer online education through e-learning. The Ministry of Technology and Education and the National Council for Educational Research and Training (NCERT) are developing several online learning platforms. Other online platforms include National Knowledge Network (NKN), National Academic Depository (NAD), e-PG Pathshala (e-Content), Employment Authorization (NEAT), National Project for Enhanced Technology-Enabled Learning (NPTEL), and e-PG Pathshala (e-Content). However, it primarily serves educational purposes.

The SWAYAM (Online Courses for Teachers) project of the Government of India offers an integrated platform and site for online courses for instructors, making it one of the reputable MOOC domains.

Technology and its Limitations

Thanks to technology, work may now be completed quickly and easily in every profession. Additionally, technology offers educational establishments a range of instructional strategies that aid in tying together the teaching and learning process for teachers and students. Education institutions are compelled to use the capabilities of technology for teaching and learning in developing nations like India due to a shortage of teaching staff or high-quality educational institutions

Teachers can employ cutting-edge online teaching techniques during the pandemic when physical education is not feasible because of quarantine. Although face-to-face learning has benefits, teachers must now act as mentors and counselors, making pupils feel like they are sitting in a classroom and taking notes. In addition, teachers are expected to provide more videos, messages, comments, and feedback following an online interaction between them and their students, mainly if the entire session is digitally recorded. The course will be thorough and insightful. Beyond that, though, there are a lot of creative ways to employ technology to enhance online education and learning.

While modern technology provides various online learning options, it also has some disadvantages, particularly in underdeveloped nations like India, where access to even essential internet services is problematic. Several pupils need home computers or internet connections. Attendance for online classes will suffer significantly as a result. Online courses are more demanding than in-person ones, according to a graduate student. Every class has a mandatory online attendance requirement, therefore occasionally internet issues prevent grades from being recorded. As a result of procrastination, I frequently missed crucial chapters or classes.

Challenges in Online Classes

Teaching online courses is a challenge for many professors in higher education. As you must connect to the internet and deliver lectures using laptops, PCs, and cellphones, online education is not simple. Both teachers and students still encounter difficulties with online courses.

Teaching and curriculum development are only part of education. Nevertheless, it's more about interaction, frank debate, mentoring of ideas, and conversations that address each student's difficulties while paying attention to their expression. Teachers try all of these strategies in online classes, but many students are unable to communicate frequently due to connectivity concerns. Students struggle because they are unable to participate in online classes in the same manner that they can in traditional classroom settings.

Online and in-person teaching are not equivalent, but in-person instruction has the advantage of making eye contact with students, which helps determine whether they truly grasped what was being taught. Rules that instructors teach. In comparison to online classes, B.Kom. Computer applications students from the previous year reported being more engaged and enthusiastic in traditional, in-person theoretical and practical classes.

A large number of brand-new educational institutions have launched their online curricula utilising their own materials, including webinar hosting, video recordings, and online seminars. On the other hand, mentorship, interpersonal relationships, and brainstorming from the viewpoint of the student are not included in online education. They won't get the academic outcomes they want unless both teachers and pupils are comfortable using the technology.

Future of Online Education

What the future of online learning is the central question right now. Many difficulties that instructors and students face are highlighted in this study. According to the faculty, only some students can access online lectures, which indicates that this is a problem. In addition, access to the Internet and smartphones might be difficult for students in urban areas. Hence, for educational institutions to fully profit from online learning, connecting and supporting students is their main duty. Effective implementation of technology is a must for educational institutions. If your institution is unable to achieve that, online education is useless and you won't receive the academic outcomes you want.

Higher education only sometimes involves doing online coursework, exams, or other tasks. Students need to acquire the necessary knowledge, abilities, and other things in labs to be ready to participate actively in the workforce. In the present, this is acceptable, but what if students don't perform well academically? Due to his lack of understanding, the student will need help with various challenges associated with online classes, hindering him from landing the job he wants. Many students express frustration with voice interruptions, slow internet, and unclear communication. Colleges must overcome these obstacles if they want to achieve successful academic outcomes in terms of outcomes, internships, and placements. Because many educational institutions are doing their best in this circumstance, nobody is certain of what will occur in the future at this time.

Today, during the epidemic, numerous educational institutions concur that a solid technical foundation is required to build a uniform online learning platform. Open-source programs like Google and Zoom should not be used for online classes, but students and teachers should receive education to improve academic performance.

Schools, teachers, and students are being compelled, like never before, to adopt online learning thanks to COVID-19. The public has been made aware of the value of online education for the previous 5-6 years, and the government has proposed numerous initiatives; nevertheless, as a result of Corona 19, all teachers are now required to teach and learn. In addition, according to most educational institutions nationwide, online learning platforms must be standardized. Using mobile apps like Zoom or Google apps is not enough; they also need to be thoughtfully created and prepared for use by teachers and students. Considering the various challenges that disciplines and institutions must also comprehend, it is also necessary to assess the nature of this platform and how students learn using different online tools and approaches.

Conclusions:

Although in-person teaching is more pleasant for kids, all students and teachers must incorporate online instruction into their curricula in the contemporary epidemic. Online courses should be taken seriously by both students and instructors. Students and professors should participate in orientation sessions or quick methods to help them become more familiar with the technology tools to prevent internet outages or other technical concerns. Teachers must establish a personal connection with each student they teach online to encourage consistent attendance and compliance. Both students and teachers can overcome difficulties and realize the objectives of online education by selecting the appropriate technology. Students can also get ready for career orientation and careers.

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